

University Marine Energy Research Community

2023 Conference

4-6 October | Durham, NH, USA

Development and Testing of a Small WEC for Numerical Simulation Validation

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Abstract: A small-scale (~2m diameter) wave energy converter (WEC) has been developed to collect open-water performance data for validating the numerical simulation of a 4-body (3 buoyant arms and a main body) oscillating body type wave energy converter design. This WEC has been numerically simulated in both WEC-Sim and ProteusDS. A prototype of this system has been built to validate these numerical simulations, with initial at-sea testing demonstrating prototype functionality. To assess mechanical power extraction and produced electrical power, both mechanical power (torques times rotational velocity) and produced electrical power are recorded by the prototype. To determine mechanical power each shaft is fitted with strain gauges that feed voltages into a Wheatstone bridge to calculate torsional moments. Additionally, the system has four IMUs for monitoring the relative rotational speeds of the arms with respect to the main body, with one IMU attached to each arm and the fourth to the main body. To control torque and produce electrical power each arm drives a stepper motor with a planetary gearbox that creates an alternating current as the arms undulate up and down, which is fed into a full bridge rectifier to convert it into direct current that can be used for battery charging.

Keywords: Wave Energy Conversion; Numerical Simulation; WecSim

1. Introduction

Wave energy converters (WECs) take the potential and kinetic energy available within a wavefield and convert it into electrical energy. Numerous WEC design types are currently being developed for a variety of applications, which are commonly classified as 1) Overtopping WECs where water is collected above the mean waterline and the resulting potential energy is converted to electricity, 2) Oscillating Water Column WECs where wave motions are used to force air through bi-directional wind turbines, and 3) Oscillating Body WECs where waves move part or all of the WEC and these motions are the basis for power production. Oscillating body WECs are currently the primary design type being developed, and these systems are being designed as standalone power plants capable of generating several kW of power from one WEC, for use within wave energy farms, and for “Powering the Blue Economy” applications where they will support power needs of offshore applications that are not connected to the main power grid and often have relatively modest power needs. The conversion of mechanical power to electrical power within Oscillating Body WECs can be achieved through a variety of mechanisms that utilize hydraulics, pneumatics, linear induction, and rotating motors/generators to convert wave energy into electrical energy.

To provide modest (<100W) electrical power to offshore applications a small (~2m diameter) oscillating body WEC design was developed with a focus on producing electrical power from within the Great Lakes of the US [1]. A

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prototype of this system was then built and tested both in the Great Lakes and in a wave tank, demonstrating both functionality and power production [1].

This paper presents the numerical modeling of this WEC using both ProteusDS [2] and WEC-Sim [3] (Section 2). It then discusses the development of an experimental WEC specifically built to validate numerical model-based predictions (Section 3). Section 4 discusses numerical simulation results and an optimization performed using simulation (Section 4.1), followed by a summary of initial at-sea testing of the experimental WEC developed for simulation validation (Section 4.2). Finally, conclusions and suggested future work are provided in Section 5.

2. Numerical Simulation Development

The main aim of developing this numerical model is to accurately simulate the proposed WEC in wave conditions like those expected at its intended deployment site. The deployment site chosen for both past and future testing is Lake Saint Clair. For most analyses, a wave height of 0.4 meters was used to optimize the system's performance. To better represent the choppy conditions near the shore of Lake Saint Clair, spectral data histories were extracted from a nearby wave buoy in the Great Lakes [4]. Data collected from buoy station 45026, positioned in the nearshore waters of Lake Michigan at coordinates 41.982° N; 86.619° W, were analyzed revealing that for a wave height of 0.4 meters, the mean peak wave period is 1.95 seconds.

Two software tools are utilized to numerically simulate the Platypus WEC design presented in [1]. These tools include the commercial software tool ProteusDS and the freely available tool WEC-Sim co-developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) and Sandia National Laboratory. In this section we present brief summaries of the system design, ProteusDS numerical modeling, and WEC-Sim numerical modeling.

2.1. Platypus WEC Design

The Platypus WEC was numerically modeled using the geometries and layout shown in Fig. 1, keeping consistent configurations throughout the analysis. The only system properties that were modified during the numerical simulations were the paddle mass, length for the arms, and the controller (through the friction coefficient). The center hub shape remained unchanged throughout the analysis with a weight of 22.73 kg and the paddle shape remained trapezoidal throughout the analysis with a weight of 2.5 kg or 5 kg depending on the analysis.

Fig. 1: Numerically simulated WEC dimensions showing the main body (left), a paddle (center) and full system (right).

2.2. ProteusDS Numerical Simulation

ProteusDS serves as a solver for multibody dynamics, with a primary focus on computing the real-time movement of oceanic systems as they interact with the marine environment. An important parameter within ProteusDS is the presence of a mesh composed of panels for each body, which is essential for conducting finite element analyses in the temporal domain. However, it's important to note that this approach doesn't consider the forces generated by the interaction of wakes between the components of the WEC. The fluid forces computed using this method are resolved and assigned to each individual panel of the WEC's components.

In ProteusDS, a finite element analysis in the time domain requires a panelized mesh for each body. The simulation calculates net forces on each body at individual time steps using the Morison load approach, described as follows:

$$f_m = f_D + f_{FK} + f_{AM} \quad (1)$$

where f_D is the drag force, f_{FK} is the Froude-Krylov excitation force that arises from the pressure field of the fluid acting on the body's surface and f_{AM} is the added mass or pressure force due to the fluid's acceleration around the

WEC. Each of these forces is represented as three-component vectors and is calculated separately for every rigid body. These forces are then referenced to the appropriate body-fixed frame. The simulation computes these forces at each time step to analyze the behavior of the bodies within the fluid environment.

2.3. WEC-Sim Numerical Simulation

WEC-Sim (Wave Energy Converter Simulator) is a computer software developed by the U.S. Department of Energy's National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) and Sandia National Lab. WEC-Sim models the complex interactions between wave dynamics, WEC structures, and power generation systems. The foundational modeling principles employed by WEC-Sim to compute the time-domain behavior of a WEC are centered around the hydrodynamic coefficient matrices created by a Boundary Element Model (BEM), which for the results in this paper was Capytaine (a Python-based distribution of Nemoh) [5]. These matrices serve as the basis for computing the hydrodynamic forces acting on each rigid body, subsequently enabling the determination of the accelerations for each of these bodies. These coefficients are leveraged to solve the Cummins' Equation in six degrees of freedom (6 DOF), which is used to ascertain the WEC's accelerations.

$$m\ddot{x}(t) = f_r(t) + f_{rad}(t) + f_{exc}(t) + f_v(t) + f_{moor}(t) \quad (2)$$

where \ddot{x} are the translational and rotational accelerations of the system, $f_{rad}(t)$ is the force vector due to wave radiation and added mass, $f_{exc}(t)$ is the wave excitation and diffraction force vector, $f_v(t)$ is the viscous force vector, $f_{moor}(t)$ is the mooring force vector (not used in our study), and $f_r(t)$ is the hydrodynamic restoring force vector. All the forces and \ddot{x} are presented as column vectors with six elements, where the first three relate to linear directions (x, y, z), and the remaining three pertain to rotational axes about (x, y, z).

3. Prototype Development

A prototype WEC was developed specifically to validate the numerical simulations discussed in the previous section. As such, characterizing the WEC's motion and shaft power were of primary importance, as opposed to designing a system specifically to maximize produced electrical power and/or minimizing the levelized cost of electricity (LCOE). This goal required additional electronics beyond those on the original Platypus WEC prototype presented in [1], including the sensors required to record relative arm velocity and shaft torque. The resulting design included stepper motors to generate electrical power and control the torque associated with each arm encased within motor pods as shown in Fig. 2. While the wings were the most contentious item in the design tree, the motor pods, shown in Fig. 3, were the most technically challenging. The material chosen for the main body and wings was a 5000 series aluminum due to its ability to bend without requiring annealing. Once assembled the fins and main body were filled with expanding closed-cell marine foam to ensure proper buoyancy.

Fig. 2: SolidWorks render of WEC system with the motor pressure vessels, wing surfaces, and foam removed to show internal components.

For the endcaps of the pressure vessel, it was chosen to go with 6061 aluminum as they were more cost effective and easier to machine than an alternative plastic would have been at this size. Both the fore and aft endcaps have double O-ring seals with a soft O-ring in the front to insure proper sealing and a hard O-ring in the rear for retention (Fig. 3). Though most of the system is made of aluminum, there are a couple external parts used to mount the pods and retain the bearings made by 3d printing. As this system is expected to operate in the marine environment a plastic capable of withstanding water and UV exposure was needed so PETG was chosen as it had all the properties required. These parts can be seen in Fig. 3 in the form of both the red and white pieces.

To gather data from this system one end cap on each motor pod is equipped with two cable penetrators, one for power and one for sensors and data. These are fed into the main electronics box where the system records information about power and orientation of each of the pods.

Fig. 3: Close up of Bearing Bracket and Exploded motor pod.

4. Testing and Results

4.1. Numerical Simulation Results

The initial analysis for this Wave Energy Converter (WEC) involved a comparison between two paddle weights using ProteusDS: one weighing 5 kg and the other 2.5 kg with each paddle displacing about 10 kg of seawater when fully submerged. Results presented in Fig. 4 (Left) indicated that the 5 kg paddle produced a time-averaged peak power output of 27 Watts with a torque coefficient value of $30 \text{ N} \cdot \text{m} \cdot \text{s}/\text{rad}$ while the 2.5 kg paddle design yielded just 4.9 Watts under identical torque conditions.

Fig. 4: WEC-Sim paddle weight (Left) and simulation platform (right) comparison for 0.4 m monochromatic waves.

To compare ProteusDS and WEC-Sim mean shaft power was calculated for a wave height of 0.4 m over a range of wave periods from 1.3 to 3.5 seconds (near breaking to open-ocean swells). Results show that for this case both simulation platforms provide very similar power production estimated for lower frequency waves (<2 seconds), but WEC-Sim predicts nearly twice the power output of ProteusDS for high-frequency waves (Fig. 4 – Right).

To predict WEC power production performance further a grid of wave heights and periods was constructed to analyze the power production profile of the chosen design under varying conditions. Wave heights of 0.2 m, 0.4 m, and 0.6 m were selected. Steepness values ranging from 1:7 (near-breaking waves) to 1:50 (deep-water swell) were simulated based on these heights. Corresponding wave periods were calculated for each steepness value, supplying insights into the design's performance across diverse wave scenarios. These results also show that both simulation platforms produce similar results for low frequency waves, but very different results for high frequency waves (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5: Time averaged shaft power for monochromatic wave environments: ProteusDS (left) and WEC-Sim (right).

4.2. In-Water Testing

Prior to the first ocean test, a pool test was conducted to ensure that the WEC system maintained proper buoyancy and all seals and waterproofing efforts remained watertight. Furthermore, wave motion was manually simulated on the WEC to provide hypothetical power output values and test the ability to wirelessly read data from the system. While we successfully recorded relative velocity and positional data using IMUs throughout testing, repairs

Fig. 6: Wave buoy and WEC floating during ocean testing.

are needed on the strain gauges before torque values can be measured. The system recorded a peak power production of 8 W from the manual simulation. The only ocean test conducted thus far was performed a mile off the coast of Dania Beach, FL. The WEC and a Sofar Spotter buoy were allowed to drift for 1.5 hrs using slack moorings (Fig. 6). The system ran smoothly for the entire test with wireless connections and data collection operating throughout. The Sofar Spotter recorded a significant wave height of 0.40 m and peak period of 4.33 s. While this WEC was designed for a similar wave height, the wave period was much lower than those where good performance was seen during the numerical simulations (Fig 5). As a result, and because two of the couplers developed some slop due to loose tolerances, the ocean test only produced a peak power of 1.92 W.

5. Conclusions

This project has made progress towards validating the performance of WEC-Sim and ProteusDS for predicting the performance of a small oscillating body WEC. However, minor systems upgrades and additional testing in multiple wave conditions are needed before this validation is complete. Once these corrections are made, further open-water testing will be conducted and WEC performance data will be recorded. Recorded wave spectra will then be fed into the WEC numerical simulations and resulting numerically predicted shaft power will be compared with those obtained through offshore testing.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank the National Science Foundation for supporting this work through EEC-1950123, ECCS-1809164, and TI-2111581.

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